

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
ROOM FINDER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
PROJECT
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ABSTRACTION

The project entitled “Mero Ghar” is web-based application developed in PHP language which allows user to find the homes and rooms according to their requirement and let them advertise their vacant rooms/house using web browsers. In present scenario customer have to visit different places in search of rooms and the owners of the house also have to make many contacts to get a decent people/family. So, using “Mero Ghar” website customer can search rooms online according to their requirement. For additional information and deals they can directly contact to the owner of the house since all the contact details of owner are displayed in the advertisement along with the room/house detail, which will definitely save the valuable time of both the searchers and the renters. This website is developed on 3-tier architecture i.e., frontend, backend and database. HTML, CSS and JavaScript are used for frontend. PHP and MYSQL are used for backend and database management respectively. So, this website is developed to help the people to save their time in searching suitable rooms and co-operative customer.

Keywords: PHP, MYSQL, frontend, backend, searchers, renters;

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1. Introduction

Mero Ghar is a web-based application that allows user to find the homes and rooms according to their requirement and let them advertise their vacant rooms/house using web browsers. Using “Mero Ghar” website customer can search rooms online according to their requirement. For additional information and deals they can directly contact to the owner of the house since all the contact details of owner are displayed in the advertisement along with the room/house detail, which will definitely save the valuable time of both the searchers and the renters. So, this website is developed to help the people to save their time in searching suitable rooms and co-operative customer.

1.1 Problem Statement

Due to continuous flow of people in city areas for job opportunity, study and many other reasons it has been difficult for people to get a suitable room. It had been very difficult to find a room in city areas if you don't know any people in particular area. So, with the help of “Mero Ghar” website people don't have to worry about finding the rooms. They will have many room options in their hand. Therefore, this website is developed to help those people who face difficulty in finding rooms. Also, this website provides the contact information of room owner so that they can directly talk to the owner and make a deal.

1.2 Project Objectives

- To save valuable time of people in finding the rooms.
- To provide variety of rooms option and to help people in getting room according to their need and budget.
- To help the people who have vacant room to find the renters.

1.3 Significance of the Study

The study investigates the need of room finding website. Nowadays people are compelled to pay whatever their house owner wants them to pay. So, through this website it will create competition between the owners and we believe there will be the fixed price range set according to the facility provided in room. More option gives relief to high rent payers and also to the owners whose rooms stay vacant for many months due to lack of advertisement.

3.Methodology

For this project we will be using incremental model of software process model, in which whole requirement is divided into various module. In this model, each module goes through the requirements, design, implementation and testing phases. Every subsequent release of the module adds function to the previous release. The process continues until the complete system is achieved.

3.1 SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT LIFECYCLE

The framework that we planned to incorporate for developing this project is the Incremental model. This model combines a linear sequential model with the iterative prototype model. In each increment, new features are added. The phases of the linear sequential model are Analysis, Design, Coding, and Testing. The software repeatedly passes through these phases in iteration after delivery of an increment with progressive changes.

Fig 1: Incremental model

3.1.1 Analysis phase: In this phase, requirements to develop the system will be identified and the system functional requirements will be understood in order to develop the desired system.

3.1.2 Design phase: In this phase, the outcome of the analysis phase i.e. SRS (Software Requirement Specifications) would be translated into system's design. DFD, E-R diagram, use case diagram will be developed.

3.1.3 Coding phase: In this phase, coding will be done according to the system design and the working system will be developed by the end of the process.

3.1.4 Testing phase: In this phase, the system will be tested. With each testing, certain changes will be made according to the suggestion. The change will be applied to the system in successive increment manner until the satisfactory system is achieved.

3.2 Tools to be used

TOOLS	PURPOSE
Sublime Text Editor	Official IDE for website development
GitHub	Manage Source Code
XAMPP & a Text editor for PHP	Testing Suite for connecting apps to an external database.

4.PROJECT TASK AND TASK SCHEDULE

S. N	Task	Duration (In days)	Person
1.	Requirement analysis and specification	10	Ashish, Rajan
2.	System design	8	Ashish, Rajan
3.	Coding	45	Ashish, Rajan
4.	Database design	20	Ashish, Rajan
5.	Testing and debugging	7	Ashish, Rajan
6.	Documentation	20	Ashish, Rajan

1.1 E-R diagram

The ER Diagram is a pictorial representation of the overall logical structure of the system's database. The ER Diagram of our system is given below.

Fig2: E-R diagram

1.2 DFD Diagram

Fig 3: DFD diagram

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